

Public School Teachers' Immediacy as Predictor of Learners' Motivation in Asuncion, Davao Del Norte

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Abstract. The study aimed to investigate the influence of teacher immediacy on the learners' motivation. In this study, a descriptive correlational method was employed, and the researcher selected 170 Grade 6 learners in the Asuncion District, Division of Davao del Norte. A stratified random sampling technique was used to determine the respondents. A non-experimental, quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational method was used. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte were rated as moderately extensive. Furthermore, correlation analysis showed a significant relationship between teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. Regression analysis revealed that teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal warmth, significantly influenced learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. The Department of Education (DepEd) should develop and implement policies that foster a supportive and inclusive school culture. The Department of Education should develop and implement teacher training programs that focus on cultivating instructional immediacy skills. Provide ongoing professional development opportunities to ensure teachers can effectively apply these skills in the classroom.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management
2. teacher immediacy
3. learners' motivation
4. descriptive correlational study

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1. Introduction

In education, to establish a positive relationship with learners, the teacher must be aware of their own behavior and the response of their learners to this behavior. As a teacher interacts with their students during the educational process, they have the primary responsibility for the quality and efficiency of the interaction. For instance, a teacher may fulfill this responsibility more efficiently by adopting immediate behaviors in the educational process, which also involves the communication process. Also, teachers are considered the most outstanding component of any educational system. Therefore, the adequacy of education depends on the effectiveness of the teachers in that educational system, which is the most critical factor in determining learners' success. Across the globe, researchers have long recognized the role of teachers' immediacy in shaping learners' drive to succeed academically. Shakir (2021) initially

established that verbal and non-verbal immediacy behaviors, such as using students' names and maintaining eye contact, were positively associated with learner motivation and participation. More recently, Hu and Wang (2023) confirmed that teacher immediacy contributes to the formation of stronger relational ties between instructors and students, leading to higher levels of academic engagement. Likewise, Zheng (2021) observed that students exposed to teachers who demonstrate warmth, enthusiasm, and open communication report greater interest in classroom tasks, underscoring the universal importance of immediacy in sustaining motivation. The significance of teacher immediacy has also been highlighted in diverse educational settings where cultural and institutional challenges exist. Derakhshan et al. (2023) revealed that immediacy behaviors consistently improve students' affective learning, regardless of their cultural background, indicating that the concept transcends cultural boundaries. Building on these perspectives, several scholars have also emphasized that the learning climate created by teachers has a profound influence on student motivation. According to Saidah et al. (2019), when students perceive their teachers as supportive and approachable, they are more likely to invest effort and persist in learning tasks. Similarly, Amerstorfer and Munster-Kistner (2021) noted that motivation thrives in environments where learners feel connected and valued, reinforcing the role of teacher-student interactions in academic engagement. In the Philippine setting, learner motivation has been consistently linked to the quality of teacher-student interaction. Palomo and Chagas (2022) noted that Filipino learners tend to be more engaged when teachers display supportive behaviors, such as encouragement and recognition, which foster a sense of belonging in the classroom. Similarly, Namoc (2023) emphasized that positive teacher communication contributes to building student confidence, which is crucial in sustaining motivation. Along the same line, Delos Reyes and Torio (2021) argued that the role of teachers in the Philippines extends beyond instruction, as their ability to establish rapport and demonstrate immediacy significantly influences students' willingness to learn. Moreover, public school classrooms in the country present unique challenges where teacher immediacy becomes highly relevant. A study by Campano (2019) highlighted that overcrowded classes often lead to learners feeling neglected; however, teachers who use immediacy behaviors, such as calling students by name and moving around the classroom, help mitigate disengagement. Likewise, Lopez (2023) observed that Filipino students exhibited increased classroom participation when their teachers incorporated humor and personalized feedback into their teaching practices. Furthermore, Geronimo and Olegario (2020) found that teacher warmth and approachability were strongly correlated with students' academic motivation, particularly in low-resource public schools. Furthermore, studies have shown that teacher immediacy plays a crucial role in motivating learners in the changing educational landscape of the Philippines. Lapitan et al. (2021) noted that during remote and blended learning, students were more motivated when teachers communicated consistently and showed empathy through virtual platforms. Similarly, Nuñez and Gula (2023) emphasized that Filipino learners excel when they perceive their teachers as approachable, regardless of the instructional mode. Supporting this, Toquero (2021) reported that students' motivation in public schools significantly increased when teachers used inclusive language and interactive strategies that reduced the perceived distance between them and their learners. In the local context of the Davao Region, teacher-student interaction has been shown to influence learners' motivation in public schools significantly. Quines and Relacion (2022) noted that students in some areas of Davao responded more posi-

tively to their lessons when teachers displayed immediacy behaviors such as encouragement, humor, and personalized attention. The study further emphasized that learners became more engaged and motivated when teachers created a warm and supportive classroom atmosphere, highlighting the importance of immediacy practices in sustaining student participation despite common challenges in local public schools.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—

1.1.1. *Teacher Immediacy*—Teacher immediacy refers to verbal and non-verbal behaviors that foster closeness, warmth, and approachability between teachers and students (Derakhshan, 2021). Studies show that immediacy enhances student engagement, motivation, and satisfaction by creating a supportive and interactive learning environment (Hu Wang, 2023; Finkielsztein, 2020; Xie & Derakhshan, 2021). It strengthens student-teacher relationships, reduces anxiety, and promotes trust and communication (Pishghadam et al., 2019; Laconelli & Anderman, 2021). Non-verbal cues such as gestures and proximity further improve motivation (Liu, 2021), while immediacy also predicts success in online learning (Schultz, 2022).

High immediacy encourages class participation, collaboration, and openness (Zheng, 2021) and is linked to academic success (Liu, 2021; Bhatti, 2020). It also enhances school climate and culture, promoting effective communication across the school community (Richmond & McCroskey, 2020; Napier, 2021). Moreover, it boosts teacher credibility and student well-being while supporting effective classroom management and parent engagement (Kianinezhad, 2023; Sozer, 2019; Qin, 2022). By generating positive emotions, fostering rapport, and supporting differentiated instruction, immediacy advances both individual learning and broader educational goals (Li et al., 2020; Asim et al., 2020; Shoaib, 2023).

Indicators of Teacher Immediacy. Inter-

personal communication encourages two-way exchanges that build trust and rapport (Sozer, 2019; Tera, 2023; Franz, 2021; Xie & Derakhshan, 2021). Interpersonal warmth fosters care, trust, and emotional safety, creating a positive classroom atmosphere (Sun et al., 2019; Li et al., 2023; Wojciszke et al., 2019). Intimacy, within professional boundaries, strengthens personal connections, engagement, and motivation (Start & Bettini, 2021; Tackie, 2022; Shin & Bolkan, 2021; Kim & Asbury, 2020).

1.1.2. *Learners' Motivation*—Motivation involves internal and external factors that sustain academic effort (Morris et al., 2022). Moderate motivation promotes persistence, realistic goal-setting, adaptability, and balanced stress management (Celikoz, 2019; Latham, 2023; Stockinger et al., 2021; Chaudhuri, 2020). It enhances peer relationships, attendance, and active participation (Pinter et al., 2020; Kilday & Ryan, 2022), while supporting positive school culture and reducing behavioral issues (Muhammad, 2021; Amtu, 2020). Motivation also nurtures growth mindset and resilience (Mesler et al., 2021; Dembo & Seli, 2019).

Indicators of Motivation. Intrinsic motivation drives curiosity, persistence, and self-directed learning, improving achievement (Grigorescu, 2020; Cherry, 2023; Shin & Bolkan, 2021; Brandt, 2020). Self-efficacy reflects students' belief in their abilities, influencing persistence, problem-solving, and collaboration (Borkowski & Thorpe, 2023; Ansong et al., 2019; Majer, 2019; Dehbozorgi et al., 2021). Self-determination fosters autonomy, self-regulation, and well-being by aligning academic goals with personal values (Ryan & Deci, 2020; Howard et al., 2021; Niemiec & Ryan, 2019; Krause et al., 2019).

1.1.3. *Link Between Immediacy and Motivation*—Instructional immediacy—through approachability, enthusiasm, and feedback—directly enhances learners' motivation, engagement, and growth mindset (Shoaib, 2023;

Wang & Lehman, 2021; Hu & Wang, 2023; Paris, 2022; Sozer, 2019). By reducing communication barriers and fostering supportive relationships, teacher immediacy encourages participation, confidence, and sustained academic success.

1.2. Synthesis—The literature reviewed across different contexts underscores the crucial role of teacher immediacy in predicting learners' motivation. At the global level, studies have shown that teacher behaviors such as eye contact, humor, and encouragement promote stronger engagement and persistence among students. These findings are echoed in the Philippine setting, where teacher immediacy has been linked to improved classroom participation and motivation, even within overcrowded and under-resourced public schools. Scholars argue that Filipino learners are more willing to invest effort in learning when teachers establish rapport and demonstrate warmth and approachability. Locally, in Davao del Norte, evidence suggests that learners respond more positively when teachers employ immediacy behaviors, such as encouragement, humor, and personalized attention. Taken together, these studies affirm that teacher immediacy is not only a supportive strategy but also a predictive factor in sustaining learners' motivation, making it an essential focus for strengthening public school instruction. Moreover, a significant relationship between teacher immediacy and learner motivation is crucial for effective teaching and learning, particularly in the context of the Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. Teacher immediacy, which refers to verbal and nonverbal behaviors that reduce the psychological distance between teachers and students, can positively impact student motivation and engagement, leading to improved learning outcomes. Teacher immediacy behaviors, such as smiling, maintaining eye contact, and using humor, can create a positive learning environment, thereby increasing student motivation and engagement. This can

lead to better academic results. The specific context of Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division, can present unique challenges or opportunities for enhancing teacher-student relationships and motivation. Research supports a positive correlation between teacher immediacy and student motivation across different educational levels and contexts. Teacher training programs can equip educators with the skills and strategies to effectively implement immediacy behaviors in their classrooms, including verbal and nonverbal communication techniques. In conclusion, fostering a strong connection between teachers and students through immediacy behaviors can significantly impact student motivation and learning.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—

The study is anchored on Ryan and Deci's (2017) Self-Determination Theory of Motivation which refers to intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and details how these motives influence situational reactions in several areas, as well as social, cognitive, and personality development. It focuses on the fundamental psychological requirements of autonomy, competence, and relatedness, as well as their critical role in self-determined motivation, well-being, and progress. Ultimately, it examines how the social and cultural context can either facilitate or hinder people's fundamental psychological needs, their perceived sense of self-direction, performance, and overall well-being. The current study is grounded in the proposition of Sozer (2019), which posits the influence of teacher immediacy on learners' motivation. The same author postulated that teacher immediacy behaviors could lead to positive learning outcomes and improve students' performance by elevating their motivation to learn. Likewise, Zhang (2022) postulated that verbal teacher immediacy behaviors could play an essential role in learners' motivation towards academic achievement. Furthermore, Liu (2021) postulated that increased degrees of immediacy could

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

contribute to positive reinforcement, which motivates students to interact with the teacher while also creating a sense of reward or pleasant valence. The likelihood of high immediacy could increase students' desire to take on the role of active learners in the classroom. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable of the study is teacher immediacy, which refers to the communication behaviors that reduce the perceived distance between teachers and students. According to Sozer (2019), teacher immediacy is measured in terms of interpersonal communication. The first indicator of teacher immediacy in this study is interpersonal communication or the process that involves information, ideas, and feelings being exchanged verbally or non-verbally between two or more people; interpersonal warmth or

the constellation of traits related to perceived favorability of the other person's intentions toward us, including friendliness, helpfulness, and trustworthiness; and intimacy or the state of being close, familiar, or affectionate with another person or group which can involve mental, emotional, or physical aspects of the relationship. The dependent variable is learners' motivation, or the person's effort to accomplish their duties, dedicating the necessary effort and continuing it. The measure of learners' motivation according to Chaudhuri (2020) are intrinsic motivation or the motivation to engage in a behavior due to inherent satisfaction of the activity; self-efficacy or the beliefs about someone's capabilities to exercise control over events that affect their lives; and self-determination or the ability to decide for oneself without influence from outside.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary aim of this study was to determine which domain of teacher immediacy significantly influ-

ences learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of public-school teachers' immediacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division, in terms of:
 - (1) interpersonal communication;
 - (2) interpersonal warmth; and

- (3) intimacy?
- (2) What is the extent of learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte in terms of:
 - (1) intrinsic motivation;
 - (2) self-efficacy; and
 - (3) self-determination?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between public school teachers' immediacy and learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division?
- (4) Which among the domains of public-school teachers' immediacy significantly influences learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division?

1.5. *Hypothesis*—The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between public school teachers' immediacy and learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. H02: None of the domain of public-school teachers' immediacy significantly influence learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Teacher Immediacy. In this study, the independent variable is described in terms of interpersonal communication, interpersonal warmth, and intimacy. Learners' Motivation. In this study, the dependent variable is described in terms of the following indicators: intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-determination.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the research framework, encompassing the chosen design, participant selection, data collection tools, information gathering procedures, and data analysis methods. These elements collectively ensure a systematic approach to addressing the study's objectives.

2.1. *Research Design*—this study, the researcher employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It was formed through a deductive approach, where emphasis was placed on testing theories, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. Non-experimental research, on the other hand, is research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Remler and Van Ryzin (2021), was a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. In this study, the researcher examined teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. Specifically, the study focused on the relationships among variables to determine the significance of the relationship between the two variables. In this study, the use of a descriptive-correlational approach was appropriate because the researcher focused solely on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and no experiment was conducted in a controlled setting.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The respondents of the study were the grade 6 learners in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. In this study, the 170 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling was a method of sampling

that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Howell et al. (2020), in stratified random sampling, also known as stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were used to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those bona fide enrolled grade 6 learners in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, those who have good moral character, and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not take into account the learners' gender and

socio-economic status.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed questionnaires adapted from various studies and modified to fit the context of the respondents in this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument, which concerned teacher immediacy, was adapted from Sozer's (2019) study and used to measure teacher immediacy behavior, comprising three domains: interpersonal communication, interpersonal warmth, and intimacy. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all items in each dimension under their respective domains. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale, which is as follows: 5–Always, 4–Oftentimes, 3–Sometimes Agree, 2–Seldom, 1–Never Disagree. As a guide in determining the level of Teacher Immediacy, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher's immediacy is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher's immediacy is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher's immediacy is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher's immediacy is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher's immediacy is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the Learners' Motivation adapted from Chumbley, Haynes, and Stofer (2015).) which is divided into four domains: intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, self-determination, and grade motivation. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under each domain. In answering the question-

naire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale, which is as follows: 5–Always, 4–Oftentimes, 3–Sometimes Agree, 2–Seldom, 1–Never Disagree. As a guide in determining the level of Learners' Motivation, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

The questionnaire was pilot-tested in a nearby school and yielded a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.700, indicating that the questionnaire had a high level of internal con-

sistency. The scaling was performed by setting one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point, or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before administering the instrument, it

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4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The learners’ motivation is always manifested.
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2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learners’ motivation is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learners’ motivation is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learners’ motivation is never manifested.

was subject to validation by three experts, and revisions were made according to their expert comments.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher took steps to conduct the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public schools in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher then distributed the research instrument to the respondents after obtaining approval to conduct the study. This was conducted from May 22 to 24, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher distributed the questionnaires in accordance with health protocols. The participants in the study were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After retrieving the data from the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data by indicator. Afterward, each score was subjected to both descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires, along with supporting authors, were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. This study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher ensured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the real source of information, thereby protecting the identities of the respondents. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the participants’ consent. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the online survey results to ensure that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information.

2.6. Data Analysis—In this study, the researcher employed several statistical tools to analyze the collected data. The Mean was utilized to describe and summarize the levels of teacher immediacy and learners’ motivation, providing insights necessary to address the first two research objectives. To examine the strength and direction of the relationship between teacher immediacy (independent variable) and learners’

motivation (dependent variable). The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used. This measure helps determine whether a significant linear association exists between the two variables, with the correlation coefficient denoted as r in the analysis. Additionally, mul-

multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the extent to which teacher immediacy influences learners' motivation, allowing the researcher to evaluate the significance and strength of this predictive relationship.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in Chapter 1. Thus, it presents the extents of teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte; the significant relationship between teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte; and the influence of teacher immediacy on the learners' motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte.

3.1. Teacher Immediacy in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte—

3.1.1. *Interpersonal Communication*—Table 1 shows that the teacher's immediacy was assessed by the respondents as moderately extensive with a category mean of 3.21, interpreted as sometimes observed in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.22 to 3.43. On the one hand, the item 'Using eye contact in communication' has a mean rating of 2.22, described as less extensive and interpreted as seldom observed by the respondents. On the other hand, the item Using the words "We and Our" in communicating reflects a mean of 3.43, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the Grade 6 learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This implies that the verbal and non-verbal communication strategies used by teachers to establish a positive and engaging relationship with their students, foster-

ing a supportive learning environment, were sometimes observed by the learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This supports Franz's (2021) idea that interpersonal communication at moderate levels promotes student engagement. Teachers who engage with students in a friendly yet focused manner encourage active participation, discussion, and collaboration in the classroom. According to Tera (2023), moderate levels of interpersonal communication contribute to creating a comfortable and inclusive learning atmosphere. Teachers who strike a balance in their communication styles make students feel at ease while maintaining a professional and authoritative presence. Establishing a distinct discipline within communication studies, the examination and instruction of interpersonal communication have continuously been subject to critical review and reevaluation, as Borisoff McMahan (2017) provide a comprehensive overview.

3.1.2. *Interpersonal Warmth*—Results in Table 2 show that teacher immediacy in terms of interpersonal warmth got a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.32, which means that this domain of teachers' instructional immediacy is sometimes observed by the learners

in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.49 to 4.18. The item Knowing each of my students' names reflects a mean rating of 2.49, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item seldom observed. Meanwhile, the item Ex-

Table 1. Teacher Immediacy in Terms of Interpersonal Communication

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Using eye contact in communicating.	2.22	Less Extensive
2	Speaking using gestures and facial expressions.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
3	Having different tone of voice in communicating.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
4	Using the words “We and Our” in communicating.	3.43	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.21	Moderately Extensive

hibiting an approachable physical appearance and interpreted as item oftentimes observed. shows a rating of 4.18, described as extensive

Table 2. Teacher Immediacy in Terms of Interpersonal Warmth

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Showing sense of humor.	3.45	Moderately Extensive
2	Being friendly and always smiling.	3.14	Moderately Extensive
3	Exhibiting an approachable physical appearance.	4.18	Extensive
4	Knowing each of my students’ names.	2.49	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.32	Moderately Extensive

This means that teachers’ expressions of kindness, friendliness, and approachability towards their students are sometimes observed. This supports the idea of Sun et al. (2019) that moderate levels of interpersonal warmth contribute to the development of positive teacher-student relationships. Teachers convey a sense of care and genuine interest in their students, establishing connections that enhance the learning experience. According to Li et al. (2023), interpersonal warmth at moderate levels contributes to the creation of a supportive learning environment. Teachers provide emotional support, making students feel valued and fostering an atmosphere where learning is not only challenging but also enjoyable. It encourages student engagement.

3.1.3. *Intimacy*—Specifically, teachers’ immediacy in terms of intimacy acquired a category mean of 3.26, described as moderately extensive, which means that this domain of teacher

immediacy is sometimes observed in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.02 to 3.46. It is noteworthy that item Using physical contact in conversation has a mean rating of 3.02, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes observed while item Spending time outside of class has a mean rating of 3.46, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed by the respondents. The results of Mainhard et al. (2018) revealed that teacher agency (interactive dominance or influence) and empathy (warmth or intimacy) were important for developing learners’ positive emotions, such as enjoyment. Goetz et al. (2021) noted that a higher-quality teacher-learner interpersonal relationship is correlated with greater enjoyment, while foreign language anxiety is negatively correlated with less efficient teacher-learner interpersonal relationships.

Table 3. Teacher Immediacy in Terms of Intimacy

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Spending time outside of class.	3.46	Extensive
2	Using physical contact in conversation.	3.02	Moderately Extensive
3	Being physically involved in every activity.	3.43	Extensive
4	Giving personal examples in our lesson.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.26	Moderately Extensive

This implies that the degree of personal closeness and connection between teachers and students within the boundaries of professionalism was sometimes observed in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This supports the conclusion of Start and Bettini (2021) that moderate levels of intimacy contribute to the development of trusting relationships between teachers and students. While maintaining professional boundaries, teachers convey a sense of personal connection that fosters trust and confidence in the learning process. Intimacy at moderate levels enhances emotional support in the classroom. Teachers provide a supportive and caring atmosphere, creating an environment where students

feel comfortable expressing their thoughts, concerns, and questions. Lastly, Table 4 shows the summary of teacher immediacy in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The overall mean of teacher immediacy is 3.26, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. Moreover, teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal warmth, achieved the highest mean score of 3.32, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed, while teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal communication, acquired the lowest mean score of 3.21, also described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed.

Table 4. Summary on Teacher Immediacy in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Interpersonal Communication	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Interpersonal Warmth	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Intimacy	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.26	Moderately Extensive

This means that the verbal and non-verbal behaviors that create a sense of closeness, warmth, and approachability between teachers and students in the educational setting were sometimes observed by learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This supports the findings of Hu and Wang (2023), which suggest that high levels of teacher immediacy contribute to increased student engagement. When teachers demonstrate warmth, enthusiasm, and approachability, students are more likely to feel

connected to the learning process and actively participate in class activities. According to Finkielsztein (2020), teacher immediacy creates a positive and supportive learning atmosphere. Students feel comfortable expressing their thoughts, asking questions, and seeking clarification, contributing to a more inclusive and open classroom environment.

3.2. Learners' Motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte—

3.2.1. *Intrinsic Motivation*—Table 5 shows that learners’ motivation, in terms of intrinsic motivation, was described by the learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, as moderately extensive, with a category mean of 3.31. This means that learners’ motivation is sometimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.72 to 4.13. The

item ‘Being curious about discoveries in our subject’ shows a mean rating of 2.72, described as less extensive and interpreted as this item rarely being manifested by the Grade 6 learners. Further, the item Having a lesson they learn is relevant to their life has a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested by the Grade 6 learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte.

Table 5. Learners’ Motivation in Terms of Intrinsic Motivation

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Learning a new lesson is interesting.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
2	Enjoying learning new lessons.	3.42	Extensive
3	Having lesson they learn is relevant to their life.	4.13	Extensive
4	Being curious about discoveries in our subject.	2.72	Moderately Extensive
5	Learning new lessons make their lives more meaningful.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.31	Moderately Extensive

This implies that the internal drive and inherent interest that individuals have in engaging in an activity for its own sake, deriving satisfaction, enjoyment, or a sense of fulfillment from the activity itself, are sometimes manifested in learners. This supports the result of Shin and Bolkan (2021) that moderately intrinsically motivated students demonstrate increased effort and commitment to their academic pursuits. They are willing to invest time and energy in their studies due to a genuine interest in the subject matter, contributing to improved academic achievement. According to Cherry (2023), moderately extensive intrinsic motivation contributes to sustained interest in learning. Students with moderate inherent motivation are more likely to maintain curiosity and enthusiasm for academic subjects over time, leading to consistent engagement in their studies.

Grade 6 learners sometimes exhibited it. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.25 to 3.78. The table further reveals that the item, being confident that they will do well on learning new lessons, has a mean rating of 2.25, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item that seldom manifests. Meanwhile, the item Being confident that they will do well on our subject has mean rating of 3.78 described as extensive and interpreted as learners’ motivation is oftentimes manifested by the learners. This implies that learners’ belief in their capability to perform academic tasks and achieve desired outcomes successfully is sometimes manifested in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This supports the result of Olave (2019), which indicates that moderate levels of self-efficacy led to increased academic confidence. Students with moderate self-efficacy beliefs feel more assured in their ability to tackle academic challenges, leading to a positive impact on educational achievement.

3.2.2. *Self-Efficacy*—This domain’s learners’ motivation, in terms of self-efficacy, as shown in Table 6, reflects a moderately extensive category mean of 3.21, indicating that

Table 6. Learners’ Motivation in Terms of Self-Efficacy

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Believing they can earn a higher grade in the subject.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
2	Being sure they can understand a new lesson.	3.45	Extensive
3	Being confident that they will do well in learning new lessons.	2.25	Less Extensive
4	Believing they can master new knowledge and skills in our subject.	3.31	Moderately Extensive
5	Being confident that they will do well on our subject.	3.78	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.21	Moderately Extensive

According to Ansong et al. (2019), moderate self-efficacy is associated with higher goal setting and aspirations. Students with moderate self-efficacy are more likely to set challenging yet achievable academic goals, contributing to a sense of purpose and direction in their studies.

3.2.3. *Self-Determination*—This domain, as shown in Table 7, has a category mean of 3.10, described as moderately extensive. It was interpreted that this domain of students’ motivation is sometimes manifested in Grade 6 learners. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.10 to 3.89. Specifically, the item Studying hard to learn new lessons has a mean rating of 2.10, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item that seldom manifests. The item Spending a lot of time learning new lessons reflects a mean rating of 3.89 described as extensive and interpreted as

item oftentimes manifested. The result indicates that the ability of individuals to autonomously regulate their behavior, make choices, and set goals based on their own values and interests is sometimes evident in learners. This supports the idea of Howard et al. (2021) that moderate self-determination is associated with intrinsic motivation. Students with moderate levels of self-determination are more likely to engage in learning activities for the inherent satisfaction and joy of learning, contributing to increased academic engagement and achievement. Likewise, Ryan et al. (2019) noted that moderate self-determination leads to goal setting aligned with personal values. Students with moderate self-determination are more likely to set academic goals that align with their intrinsic interests and values, fostering a sense of purpose and contributing to academic achievement.

Table 7. Learners’ Motivation in Terms of Self-Determination

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Putting enough effort into learning new lessons.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
2	Using strategies to learn new lessons well.	3.62	Extensive
3	Spending a lot of time learning new lessons.	3.89	Extensive
4	Studying hard to learn new lessons.	2.10	Less Extensive
5	Preparing well for our lessons’ tests.	2.56	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.10	Moderately Extensive

Lastly, Table 8 presents a summary of learners' motivation in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. As shown in the table, learners' motivation obtained an overall mean score of 3.21, with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive, interpreted as sometimes manifested. Adding more, results on Table 8 show that learners' motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation

acquired the highest mean score of 3.31, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. In contrast, learners' motivation in terms of self-determination acquired the lowest mean score of 3.10, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the Grade 6 learners in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte.

Table 8. Summary on Learners' Motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Intrinsic Motivation	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Self-Efficacy	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Self-Determination	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.21	Moderately Extensive

The results indicate that the desire and willingness to engage in learning activities, set and achieve goals, and persist in the face of challenges are sometimes manifested in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This finding aligns with Latham's (2023) view, which suggests that it enables students to set realistic and achievable goals. They are motivated enough to strive for success, but maintain a balanced approach that prevents setting overly ambitious or unattainable objectives, promoting a sense of accomplishment. According to Celikoz (2019), moderate levels of motivation contribute to sustained effort and persistence in academic tasks. Students with moderate motivation are more likely to remain engaged in their studies, even when faced with challenges or setbacks, which in turn increases their likelihood of academic success.

Relationship Between Teacher Immediacy and Learners' Motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

The results of the analysis of the relationship between teacher immediacy and learners'

motivation in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis, using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, was employed to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 9 illustrates the relationships between teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The results indicate that teacher immediacy has a significant positive relationship with learners' motivation, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.328, p < 0.05$). It means that as the level of the teacher's immediacy changes, learners' motivation also significantly changes. Adding more, the table also indicates that teacher immediacy in terms of interpersonal communications; interpersonal warmth; and intimacy correlated considerably with learners' motivation in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .411, p < 0.05$), ($r = .262, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .325, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 9. Relationship Between Teacher Immediacy and Learners' Motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Interpersonal Communication	0.411*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Interpersonal Warmth	0.262*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Intimacy	0.325*	0.000	Reject H ₀
Overall Teacher Immediacy	0.328*	0.000	Reject H ₀

Note. *Significant at $p < .05$.

This supports the view of Wang and Lehman (2021) that immediate instructors are more likely to provide personalized feedback and encouragement. This individualized attention makes students feel recognized and supported, boosting their confidence and motivation to excel in their academic pursuits. Teacher immediacy plays a crucial role in fostering a positive classroom environment. A positive and supportive atmosphere encourages students to feel comfortable, valued, and motivated to contribute to class discussions, ask questions, and actively participate in activities.

]Influence of Teacher Immediacy on the Learners' Motivation in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

The significance of teacher immediacy's influence on learners' motivation in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 10 shows that when teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal communication, interpersonal warmth, and intimacy dimensions, is considered, the model is significant, as evidenced by the F-value of 6.759 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that teacher immediacy predicts the learners' motivation in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R-

squared value of 0.340 indicates that teacher immediacy has contributed significantly to the variability of learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte, accounting for 34.00% of the total variability. Therefore, the 66.00 % difference was attributed to factors not covered in this study. In addition, the table shows that there are domains of teacher immediacy that significantly influence the learners' motivation in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. This table also indicates that only interpersonal warmth was a significant predictor of learners' motivation. This means that the extent of learners' motivation increases by 0.271 for each unit increase in teacher immediacy in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of teacher immediacy significantly influence the learners' motivation in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. Paul et al. (2019) analyzed the impact of teachers' nonverbal immediacy behaviors on their teaching effectiveness and found no significant difference in the immediacy behaviors of male and female teachers. Moreover, they found that nonverbal immediacy behaviors had a significant influence on teaching effectiveness.

This finding aligns with Smith's (2018) study, which suggests that teacher immediacy fosters increased student engagement. When teachers demonstrate enthusiasm for the subject matter, employ engaging teaching methods, and

actively involve students in the learning process, it has a positive influence on students' motivation to participate and learn. Teacher immediacy plays a crucial role in fostering a positive learning identity. When students feel that their

Table 10. Influence of Teacher Immediacy on the Learners' Motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Teacher Immediacy	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Interpersonal Communication	.076	.072	.085	.372	Accept H ₀
Interpersonal Warmth	.271**	.256	.087	.002	Reject H ₀
Intimacy	.144	.148	.080	.073	Accept H ₀
R ² = 0.340 F-value = 6.759* p-value = 0.000					

Note. *Significant at $p < .05$.

** indicates strong significance at $p < .01$.

teacher genuinely cares about their success, it in effort in their studies. enhances their self-esteem and motivation to put

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section of the paper offers the researcher's conclusion and recommendations. The discussion is grounded in the literature reviewed in the initial chapters, and the conclusions align with the problem statements outlined earlier in the study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of teacher immediacy significantly influence learners' motivation, utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 170 Grade Six (6) learners in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, as respondents using a stratified random sampling method. The researcher utilized modified and enhanced survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure the high reliability and internal consistency of the instrument's items. Teacher immediacy in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte got an overall mean of 3.26 with a moderate to extensive descriptive rating. Additionally, teacher immediacy, as measured by interpersonal communication, interpersonal warmth, and intimacy, yielded mean scores of 3.21, 3.32, and 3.26, respectively. Learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.21, indicating a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Additionally, learners' motivation, as measured by intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-determination, yielded mean scores of 3.31, 3.21, and 3.10, respectively. Meanwhile, correlation analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between teacher immediacy and learners' motivation in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.328, p < 0.05$). Adding more, teacher immediacy in terms of interpersonal communication, interpersonal warmth, and intimacy have significant positive relationships with the learners' motivation in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .411, p < 0.05$), ($r = .262, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .325, p < 0.05$). Moreover, regression analysis revealed that teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal warmth, significantly influenced learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte, as evidenced by an F-value of 6.759 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.340 indicated that teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal warmth, contributed significantly to the variability of learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte, accounting for 34.00 % of

the total variability.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Teacher immediacy in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte was extensive. Meanwhile, the instructional immediacy of teachers, in terms of interpersonal communication, interpersonal warmth, and intimacy, received moderately extensive descriptive ratings. Learners' motivation in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte was rated as moderately extensive. Learners' motivation, in terms of intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and self-determination, is rated as moderately extensive. Teacher immediacy has a significant positive relationship with learners' motivation in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This means that as the extent of the teacher's immediacy changes, learners' motivation also significantly changes. This corroborates Wang and Lehman's (2021) proposition that immediate instructors are more likely to provide personalized feedback and encouragement. Teacher immediacy, in terms of interpersonal warmth, significantly influenced the learners' motivation in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. This affirmed that learners' motivation is a function of teacher immediacy in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This is consistent with Hu and Wang's (2023) proposition that teacher immediacy fosters increased student engagement.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The Department of Education may develop and implement teacher training programs that focus on cultivating instructional immediacy skills. Provide ongoing professional development opportunities to ensure teachers can effectively apply these skills in the classroom. The Department of Ed-

ucation (DepEd) may encourage the development of school policies that prioritize positive teacher-student relationships and instructional immediacy. Supportive policies can create a conducive environment for teachers to engage with students more effectively. School leaders may foster a positive school culture that values teacher-student relationships and acknowledges the importance of instructional immediacy. Model supportive behavior and encourage open communication between teachers and students. They may also offer leadership training to school heads that emphasizes the role of instructional immediacy in creating a positive learning environment. Equip school leaders with the skills to support and mentor teachers in implementing these strategies. Teachers may prioritize building positive relationships with students. Take the time to understand their individual needs, interests, and challenges. Establishing rapport is a foundational step in enhancing instructional immediacy. Learners may employ positive and inclusive language in both verbal and written communication. Ensure that all students feel valued and included in the learning process, fostering a sense of belonging. They should utilize active learning strategies that encourage student participation and engagement. Incorporate interactive activities, group discussions, and hands-on experiences to create a dynamic and engaging learning environment. Future Researchers may actively engage in the learning process by participating in class discussions, asking questions, and contributing to group activities. Taking an active role in learning enhances the overall experience and motivation.

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